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“BIRDSONG”

A sniff of the wood
The crunch of a leaf
The forest of my childhood
This birdsong takes me

His steps I follow
Hush as can be
Dark before the morrow
Then the birdsong I see

We aim up high
Care not the song to flee
Shoulders taut... release!
Feathers fall, his soul set free

In the forest of my memory
Laid chase to a hundred songs
In stride, my father and I
To the depths we sent them all along

Now the depths laid chase
In my reverie only I remain
My aim now taut to keep alive
This birdsong around me till my soul flies